

Thermodynamic functions⁷ for 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complex species are presented in following Table:

Complex species	ΔF° k cal mole ⁻¹	ΔH° k cal mole ⁻¹	ΔS° k cal mole ⁻¹
1:1	-6.0020	-36.1895	-0.0998
1:2	-7.6029	-68.3084	-0.2003
1:3	-9.8434	-82.4532	-0.2396

It has been found in present study that Cd(II) forms 1:3 highest complex with citrulline which corroborates the hexacoordination tendency of the metal and bidentate nature of the ligand. There is no ligand field stabilization in Cd(II), hence the stereochemistry of its complexes is determined solely by consideration of size, electrostatic forces and covalent bonding forces.

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Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constants of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) Complexes with Methylguanidoacetic Acid

R. S. SAXENA and M. K. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur-302 017

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SAXENA and coworkers¹⁻⁵ have investigated the electrochemical behaviour of some amino acids and their metal complexes which have found useful applications in biochemistry. In this communication the complexation behaviour of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions with methylguanidoacetic acid has been studied

polarographically at 25° and at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M$ NaClO₄).

Experimental

Methylguanidoacetic acid [NH.C(NH₂).N(CH₃).CH₂COOH] was obtained from B.D.H., Poole, England. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Stock solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Triton-X-100 (0.002%) was used as the maximum suppressor. Ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M$) was maintained by NaClO₄.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the polarograms against SCE as the reference electrode. The polarograms of Cd²⁺ in presence of different concentrations of the ligand were plotted at 25° and at different pH. Well defined cathodic waves were obtained at pH 7.0 in the case of Cd²⁺ and at pH 4.0 in the case of Pb²⁺ and hence all subsequent studies were made at these pH.

To investigate the reversibility and diffusion controlled nature of the cathodic waves produced by Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with methylguanidoacetic acid, the effects of change of mercury head and concentrations of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ on the wave heights were studied. For complexation studies, a series of 1.0 mM CdSO₄ and Pb(NO₃)₂ solutions containing varying concentrations (0.02 to 0.12 M) of the ligand and 0.002% Triton-X-100 were prepared. Requisite amount of NaClO₄ was added to maintain the ionic strength at $\mu=0.1 M$. Half-wave potentials were obtained from the plots of $-E_{a.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$.

Results and Discussion

Half-wave potentials were found to shift towards the more negative values with increasing ligand concentration (Table 1) showing the complexation between Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ with methylguanidoacetic acid. The appreciable differences in the diffusion currents of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions alone and in the presence of the ligand indicate that the aquo Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions differ in size of their complexes.

A plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{eff}}$ yielded straight line showing the diffusion controlled nature of the waves. The plots of $-E_{a.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$ were also linear, whose slopes indicate the reversibility of the electrode reaction. A plot of $-E_{1/2}$ as a function of $-\log C_x$ showed the formation of successive complexes and hence DeFord and Hume's method was employed for determining the various complexity functions $F_j(X)$. $F'_2(X)$ vs C_x (Figs. 1 and 2) show a horizontal line parallel to the C_x axis which indicates the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 metal-ligand complexes.

The plots of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$ and $F_2(X)$ vs ligand concentrations (Figs. 1 and 2), when extrapolated to $C_x=0$, gave values for the stability constants of

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $E_{1,2}$, i_d , α_j AND VARIOUS FUNCTIONS $F_j(X)$ FOR Pb^{2+} AND Cd^{2+} COMPLEXES WITH METHYLGUANOACETIC ACID AT 25°

C_x of ligand [M]	i_d	$E_{1,2}$	α_j			F(X)		
			α_0	α_1	α_2	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$
Pb ²⁺ complexes								
0.00	13.583	0.578	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.02	12.044	0.581	0.014	0.205	0.104	1.419	20.95	317.50
0.04	12.705	0.586	0.020	0.295	0.299	1.975	24.37	244.30
0.06	12.780	0.592	0.019	0.281	0.428	3.111	35.18	343.13
0.08	12.785	0.597	0.017	0.255	0.518	4.564	44.55	374.37
0.10	12.705	0.601	0.016	0.233	0.592	6.242	52.42	378.20
0.12	12.892	0.606	0.013	0.194	0.590	9.028	66.90	435.83
Cd ²⁺ complexes								
0.00	14.370	0.386	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.02	14.087	0.388	0.016	0.044	0.080	1.189	9.47	340.5
0.04	12.462	0.393	0.021	0.058	0.210	1.820	20.50	446.0
0.06	13.035	0.396	0.025	0.067	0.363	2.974	22.90	253.0
0.08	11.821	0.398	0.026	0.06	0.503	3.025	25.43	294.6
0.10	10.705	0.400	0.026	0.071	0.640	3.746	27.46	248.0
0.12	11.287	0.406	0.025	0.067	0.732	4.715	30.96	285.8

Fig. 1. Plots of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$ and $F_2(X)$ as a function of ligand concentrations for cadmium-methylguanoacetic acid system at 25°.

Fig. 2. Plots of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$ and $F_2(X)$ as a function of ligand concentrations for lead-methylguanoacetic acid system at 25°.

cadmium and lead complexes as follows :

$\log K_1 = 1.16$, $\log K_2 = 2.56$ for Cd^{2+} -complexes,

$\log K_1 = 0.42$, $\log K_2 = 2.38$ for Pb^{2+} -complexes.

From known stability constant data, α_j , the values of the degree of formation for each complex in a system have been calculated at 25° from the equation

$$\alpha_j = \frac{K_j (C_x)^j}{F_0(X)}$$

and are reported in Table 1.

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